

On the Resource Consumption of 2D Human Pose Estimation Services in MEC-enabled Networks

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Abstract—In this work, we overview key state-of-the-art models and algorithms for 2D Human Pose Estimation (HPE) and provide a detailed discussion on their key features, such as backbone, training dataset and key innovations. Our primary contribution is a comprehensive experimental study on the resource consumption of state-of-the-art HPE models assuming a fully containerized service environment residing at the networked edge/cloud continuum, which is constructed in the form of a Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) service compatible with the ETSI MEC architecture. The study serves as a benchmark framework for estimating the offered network, CPU, memory and GPU workload of relevant MEC applications while it also opens the road ahead for service-tailored MEC host association of users that seek to offload their edge-computing tasks in the networked edge/cloud continuum.

Index Terms—Multi-access edge computing, Resource Utilization, Human Pose Estimation, Computer Vision, Deep Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

THE increasing availability of low-cost RGB cameras, embedded in smartphones, laptops and surveillance systems, has significantly boosted the demand for video-based computer vision (CV) applications. At the same time, there has been a transition from classic image processing techniques to machine learning (ML) enabled ones, particularly those leveraging convolutional neural networks (CNNs), which shift much of the computational burden to the training phase. This trend has enabled modern deep learning (DL) models to operate on commodity devices, allowing real-time performance even in environments with limited CPU, RAM, or network resources, unlike traditional methods that often required expensive equipment or specialized sensors such as LiDAR or RGB-D cameras to achieve similar results [2]. Among the many fields of real-life applications, HPE stands out, with a wide range of applications, including activity recognition in surveillance, motion analysis in sports and physical monitoring in healthcare and workplace environments. In industrial safety applications, such as real-time hazard detection near machinery, or ergonomic monitoring on manufacturing lines, there is a demand for HPE systems that operate reliably under strict latency constraints. In parallel, edge computing and Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) architectures have attracted

a surge of interest, as they enable real-time and resource-aware processing in the near proximity of the end user [1], [3]. Nonetheless, the admission of edge computing tasks of mobile users, requires careful estimation of the network, compute and memory loads to ensure seamless and timely deployment [4], either in the form of dedicated containerized MEC applications for individual video streams, or as shared MEC service instances supporting multiple users and/or HPE pipelines. While much of the existing literature emphasizes the accuracy of 2D HPE models, little attention has been paid to the resource utilization requirements following from their deployment in natively containerized MEC-enabled environments.

In this paper, we aim to fill this gap by benchmarking three widely used HPE models that consume standard RGB input through an experimental performance study that monitors resource consumption in terms of network usage (Rx/Tx), CPU, memory and GPU utilization to support practical deployment of MEC app instances. The models were selected based on their design approach as well as the availability of open-source implementations, pre-trained weights and compatibility with deployment toolkits, like OpenVINO [5]. Our goal is to guide MEC admission control and containerized network function (CNF) deployment by selecting appropriate 2D HPE models that balance computational efficiency with deployment feasibility under practical constraints. We structure the paper as follows. Section II provides background knowledge on commonly used CNN backbones and an overview of the HPE pipeline. Section III reviews key state-of-the-art reference models for our experimental study and discusses how different configurations of the HPE pipeline affect its performance. Section IV presents our performance evaluation study in terms of network, CPU, RAM and GPU usage, while it provides benchmark values for MEC-enabled network management tailored to HPE services. Section V concludes the paper.

II. REVIEW OF THE HPE PIPELINE

A. Background knowledge

The HPE task involves the localization of human joints and their annotation as *keypoints*, by consuming visual data (images, video frames) that are used to infer the pose of one or more individuals, i.e., single- or multi-person HPE. HPE models are governed by their design strategy/method which can be typically categorized into *top-down* and *bottom-up*.

Top-down methods begin by detecting each individual in the image using a person detector with bounding boxes. A single-person pose estimation model is then applied to each detected bounding box. This pipeline benefits from leveraging

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decades of research in both object detection and articulated human modeling. However, a key drawback is scalability, since a single pose estimation is run independently for each person, meaning that the computational cost scales linearly with the number of people in the scene. Moreover, accuracy degrades in crowded scenes where bounding boxes overlap, since incorrectly merged detection will prevent accurate HPE.

Bottom-up methods, on the other hand, detect all body keypoints in the image without prior localization of individuals. The detected keypoints are then grouped into person instances using association techniques such as part affinity fields (PAFs) [6]. These methods are generally more efficient in multi-person setups, as their inference time does not scale with the number of people. They also tend to handle occlusion better in some cases, as they rely on keypoint association rather than detection box separation. However, bottom-up methods face inherent scale invariance challenges, since they must simultaneously localize keypoints across extreme size variations within the same image. This contrasts with top-down approaches that normalize scale by cropping and resizing detections.

The HPE pipeline involves the following components:

- **Input:** A single image or a sequence of video frames.
- **Person Detector:** The image is first passed through a person detector to generate bounding boxes around each individual. (top-down approaches only)
- **Backbone Network:** A convolutional neural network (CNN) extracts deep features from either the full image (bottom-up) or from cropped regions (top-down).
- **Pose Estimation Head:** Transforms the extracted features into keypoint predictions. Outputs heat maps, one per joint, indicating the probability of each pixel being that joint or the joint coordinates (x, y) within the image.
- **Post-processing:** Non-maximum suppression, tracking, or parsing is applied, especially in multi-person scenarios, to associate keypoints with specific individuals.
- **Output:** A set of keypoints, typically one set of coordinates (x, y) for each joint per person within the input, optionally accompanied by a confidence estimation score.

Keypoints represent anatomically relevant human joints (e.g., nose, eyes, shoulders, elbows, hips, knees, ankles). The number and definition of keypoints depend on the dataset. The most widely used keypoint systems include the *COCO* [7] dataset with 17 keypoints (ears, eyes, nose, shoulders, elbows, wrists, hips, knees, ankles) and the *MPII* [8] dataset with 16, slightly different, keypoints. Each keypoint is typically represented by two pixel coordinates (x, y) , and a confidence score ranging between 0 and 1, indicating its existence probability.

B. Overview of predominant CNN backbones

In this section we review three prominent CNN backbone architectures that lay the foundations of most of the existing HPE pipelines while they simultaneously exert a significant influence both on performance and computational efficiency.

VGGNet [9]: Fundamental models stemming from AlexNet [10] that are known for their straightforward design with small 3x3 convolution layers and easy implementation that attains

Index	Keypoint
0	Nose
1	Eye L
2	Eye R
3	Ear L
4	Ear R
5	Shoulder L
6	Shoulder R
7	Elbow L
8	Elbow R
9	Wrist L
10	Wrist R
11	Hips L
12	Hips R
13	Knees L
14	Knees R
15	Ankles L
16	Ankles R

Fig. 1. Example of the COCO 17 keypoint system

high accuracy. VGG-16 and VGG-19 are the most widely used variants, with the number denoting the count of convolution layers, followed by three fully connected layers, where the majority of the model's weights are concentrated. Max pooling is applied periodically every few convolution layers for down sampling. Their high computational demand led to them being overshadowed by newer, more efficient designs like *ResNet*.

ResNet [11]: Inspired by the design philosophy of VGGNet and its 3x3 convolution layers, ResNet transformed the field of deep networks by addressing the degradation problem with the introduction of residual (skip) connections, which allow the network to bypass layers. This enabled the training of deeper and more accurate networks, whereas simply adding layers to a VGGNet would result in unexpected drops in accuracy (degradation). Bottleneck design is used by the ResNet-50/101/152 variants to address the issue of growing computation cost while boosting their depth. Remarkably, ResNet-152 (152 layers) has fewer parameters than the VGG19 model.

MobileNetV2 [12]: Optimized for mobile/embedded applications that require inference with a low memory footprint by avoiding the direct creation of large intermediate tensors. It utilizes the method of inverted residual with a linear bottleneck, which differentiates it from the original *MobileNet*, by helping it to significantly reduce the parameter count. This added layer first up-scales and then filters the compressed representation of the input with a lightweight depthwise convolution. Then, it projects the extracted features back to the low-dimensional representation with a linear convolution. It achieves high-end performance both in terms of accuracy and model complexity, enabling real-time networks for object detection.

III. 2D HPE MODELS AND IMPLEMENTATION

A. Selected 2D HPE reference models

Having reviewed some of the key HPE Backbone Networks, we now shift our focus to the remaining components of some

fundamental HPE pipelines, examining their methodologies, architectures, training datasets, strengths and limitations.

OpenPose [13] pioneered a bottom-up approach using a *VGG-19* CNN backbone for initial feature extraction across the full image. Its architecture combines a multi-stage CNN with parallel branches per stage: one predicting confidence maps for keypoints and another estimating PAFs to associate body parts. The confidence maps and PAFs are iteratively refined across the stages. Finally, greedy parsing resolves keypoint associations through bipartite graph matching, which computes connection scores between candidate keypoints using line integrals through PAF vector fields, assembles full-body poses by sequentially selecting highest-scoring limb connections while enforcing one-to-one matching and geometric constraints. This crucial step handles ambiguities in crowded scenes where multiple keypoint candidates exist. OpenPose is trained using the COCO and MPII datasets for real-time multi-person estimation; yet, its deployment on resource-constrained devices is limited by its high computational complexity.

AlphaPose [14] employs a top-down approach. It first detects human bounding boxes using an off-the-shelf detector (typically *YOLOv3* or *EfficientDet*). Then, it estimates poses within each region via its *FastPose* architecture, which combines a *ResNet-50/101* backbone with symmetric integral regression for keypoint localization. To minimize missed detections, AlphaPose uses a low confidence threshold for person detection, since detector failures are irrecoverable. Accordingly, it applies a dual-stage non-maximum suppression (NMS) after detection, called Box NMS, to filter duplicate proposals as well as Pose NMS after estimation to merge redundant poses using pose similarity metrics. AlphaPose also integrates optional pose tracking, enabling consistent keypoint identities across video frames by linking poses over time using pose similarity metrics. Trained on COCO, MPII and PoseTrack datasets, it achieves high accuracy in non-crowded scenes; yet, its performance can degrade significantly under heavy occlusion, or crowding. Besides, its sequential pipeline increases the computational load, since the inference time scales linearly with the number of detected persons, while its performance depends strongly on the initial detection quality.

MoveNet (multipose-lightning) [15] employs a hybrid strategy that combines bottom-up keypoint detection with top-down grouping. Built on a *MobileNetV2* backbone with Feature Pyramid Network decoder, it uses *CenterNet*-inspired prediction heads to simultaneously detect keypoints and person centers in a single pass. The model is designed for real-time efficiency, processes dynamically resized inputs and is optimized for TensorFlow Lite/JS deployment on consumer hardware. Trained on COCO and an internal Google dataset, MoveNet excels in movement-intensive scenarios with motion blur but sacrifices precision for real-time efficiency, making it ideal for browser-based applications while less suitable for high-accuracy industrial use.

Table I summarizes key features of selected HPE models.

TABLE I
SELECTED MODELS

Algorithm	Backbone	Input size	Approach	Licence
AlphaPose	ResNet-50	256x192	Top-down	Custom non-commercial
MoveNet	MobileNet-V2	256x192	Bottom-up	Apache 2.0
Lightweight-OpenPose	MobileNet-V1	256x456	Bottom-up	Apache 2.0

B. Implementation Details

We have reviewed existing software distributions of the selected 2D HPE models described in Section III-A and selected some stable ones that come along with a list of pre-trained models, all implemented either by the original authors, or by other third parties. The selected 2D HPE models were trained using a variety of CNN backbones, configuration parameters and datasets, affecting their precision and system requirements; thus, their specific implementation greatly affects their real-life performance and resource consumption. Some of the configuration parameters that affect the accuracy of the HPE output result are discussed below. Configurable HPE-related performance parameters include the *image input resolution*, where the need for detail retention balances inference speed, which is critically important in communication-intensive settings, e.g., when the camera frames are transmitted over HTTP/IP to the model. Also, the *model complexity* in terms of CNN model width and depth, measured in millions or billions of trainable weights that reflect their memory utilization requirement. Implementations also differ in whether a GPU-optimized execution is offered, or not, with CPU-native models being more appropriate for general-purpose hardware in contrast with ones that employ GPU-accelerated software pipelines to benefit from massive parallelism, by incorporating, for example, NVIDIA’s CUDA or cuDNN. Interestingly, the OpenVINO’s OpenCL-based GPU plugin balances between those two, enabling cross-platform reproducibility over highly specialized architectures. To balance between a device’s memory capabilities and throughput, GPU implementations offer options to process several images in parallel, usually with the parameter *detpatch*, or to set the number of detected persons sent for HPE, typically with the parameter *posebatch*.

Let us now overview some of the configuration settings that we have employed throughout our experimentation study.

- OpenPose originally provides pre-trained models in *Caffe* format, primarily optimized for CUDA/cuDNN execution. In this study, we evaluate an OpenVINO-optimized variant that preserves the original topology, employing *MobileNetV1* as a feature extractor and targeting to native CPU deployment, although GPU inference is also possible. The input resolution is fixed at 256x456 pixels.
- For AlphaPose, we select the FastPose model with a ResNet-50 backbone, which run on a CPU-only setting. The input resolution is set at 256x192 pixels.
- The MoveNet Multipose Lightning was implemented by using an OpenVINO-converted model from the PINTO

zoo [16], with GPU inference not supported. The input resolution is set at a fixed 256x256 input.

OpenVINO-based instances consider *FP32* precision mode.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

A. Experimental setup

Fig. 2 illustrates the fully automated, softwarized and containerized architecture that we have employed for our experimental study [18]. The main components of our experimental setup include: the *Camera Emulation Engine (Container 1)*, which is responsible for emulating a live video camera feed using pre-recorded video data, the *MEC-enabled HPE service (Container 2)*, which is responsible for executing different HPE algorithms using the same video stream, and the HTTP Client (Container 3), which receives the keypoints output by the HPE container for further usage. For the purposes of our experimental campaign, we have further implemented a separate Monitoring Toolset (Container 4) that extracts network, CPU, memory and GPU usage statistics directly from the HPE service (container 2). All the aforementioned Containers have been built in an automated fashion using the Docker Compose framework. Its role is to start the containers in the right order, collect information about the environment (e.g. number of CPU cores, memory and GPU used), configure the experimental parameters and setup metadata (e.g., algorithm name, timestamp), dynamically name the resulting folder that will host the performance records on network, CPU, memory and GPU usage (recorded in .csv files) and collect the associated files from each container in the "Results" folder. The corresponding results were then processed and plotted in an automated fashion by using Python and the Matplotlib library. Regarding the individual Containers, the following apply:

Container 1: Emulates the video stream from an IP-based camera. For our study, we stream videos from the Panoptic Studio Dataset [17], specifically from the "Range of Motion" sequence. The Camera Emulation Engine uses the FFmpeg service to package raw video files into real-time H.264 streams. The server implements an HTTP HEAD method for OpenCV/FFmpeg probing and a HTTP GET method that handles GET requests for the H.264 stream. The video is streamed in MPEG-TS format over HTTP and is triggered depending on the logic of each HPE service model.

Container 2: This container implements a suite of different HPE algorithms and models. In particular it includes software packages for the *AlphaPose*, *OpenPose*, and *Movenet* HPE algorithms, the first based on the original Git repository and the other two based on OpenVINO implementations. The AlphaPose implementation is the only one that's GPU-accelerated, whereas the rest run exclusively on the CPU. The output of the HPE process is communicated in the form of a structured JSON file that includes the extracted keypoint values according to the COCO 17 keypoint format (Fig. 1).

Container 3: Includes an HTTP client that requests and consumes the output of the HPE service.

Container 4: Implements our tailored monitoring toolset. To derive *network usage* statistics, we exploit *BCC*-based

tools and *tcpdump* to monitor Rx and Tx throughput at a 10ms sampling rate. We do so, targeting to allow for fine-grained estimation of delay-centered parameters like jitter and latency in future implementations. For *CPU* usage we leverage lightweight tools like *top* and *ps*. We also derive *memory* statistics by focusing on the MEM RSS metric (see below), which is obtained directly by reading the VmRSS (Virtual Memory Resident Set Size) from the */proc/\$PID/status* filesystem at the kernel level. GPU-related metrics have been derived by using the NVIDIA *Nvidia-SMI* toolkit.

In our experimental campaigns we have evaluated the performance of the 2D HPE MEC Service in view of the following important key metrics:

- **Rx:** Throughput at the reception port of the HPE Service, as transmitted by the Camera Emulation Engine. It provides an estimate of the required upload throughput for end devices that stream their data to the MEC infrastructure. The metric is measured in Mbps.
- **Tx:** Throughput at the transmission port of the HPE service towards the HTTP client (Container 3) that consumes the keypoint output (JSON file) produced by the HPE service. It provides an estimate of the required download throughput for end devices that need to consume the HPE output, e.g., control rooms and/or mobile users. The metric is measured in Mbps.
- **CPU utilization:** Percentage of local/instantaneous CPU usage at the HPE Service host, e.g., the MEC host, during the implementation of the HPE service instance.
- **MEM RSS:** Resident Set Size (RSS) memory usage measured in GB. Measures the instantaneous (actual) usage of physical RAM, as opposed to memory that has been swapped out or simply reserved in the process's address space. Estimate of how much actual RAM is consumed at a given moment by the HPE service containerized.
- **GPU Utilization:** Percentage of GPU usage in runtime for the HPE service, normalized over the capacity of a single local processor (i.e., it might exceed 100%).
- **GPU Memory:** Percentage of allocated GPU memory used by the HPE service instance.
- **GPU Power:** Power consumption of the GPU used for the HPE service tasks, measured in Watts.

B. Experimental results and discussion

For the purposes of our experimental study we have considered both HD and VGA resolutions for the Panoptic Range-of-Motion video. Aiming to better highlight the instantaneous resource usage of a given HPE service instance, in Fig. 3 we plot the performance of the containerized HPE Service module assuming the HD version of the Range-of-Motion video and under all three HPE models within scope: AlphaPose, OpenPose and MoveNet (Table I). Note that all subsequent results focus on the performance of the containerized HPE service module, i.e., Container 2, which is of particular interest in the paper. To better highlight instantaneous performance trends, we have also filtered the presented results within a 100-second time window.

Fig. 2. Experimental Study Setup

Fig. 3. Instantaneous performance: HD Range-of-Motion Video.

From Figure 3 we observe that the three different implementations consume the emulated video streams from Container 1 in a different fashion, with MoveNet requesting for video frames more aggressively with an average of 3.5 Mbps, followed by AlphaPose and OpenPose with 1.8 and 0.9 Mbps respectively. Interestingly, although the input rate of the video stream is in the order of 1 to 3.5 Mbps (with peaks reaching up

to 180Mbps), the output of the HPE service, which processes the video stream and derives the semantics of human motion in the form of keypoints, is in the order of only a few Kbps, i.e., 0.07, 0.04 and 0.01 Mbps for Movenet, AlphaPose, and OpenPose, respectively. In real-life scenarios where the HPE service consumer is only interested in the semantics of human motion, it readily follows that the employment of MEC-enabled HPE services enable a significant performance trade-off between network resources and CPU/GPU/RAM resources depending on the context of the HPE service scope. For the specific setup, this reduction is shown to be in the order of two orders of magnitude, i.e., Rx/Tx ratio. Going deeper into the comparison of the three algorithms in scope, we also note that the respective Tx throughput towards the HPE service consumer (i.e., Container 4) is shown to be proportional to the FPS attained by each algorithm, with our experimental results showing that MoveNet outperforms other models with 11.28 FPS, compared to 5.83 and 3.01 FPS for AlphaPose and OpenPose, respectively. Note that the FPS metric is HPE-related and indicates the frequency with which the keypoints output is provided to the HPE service consumer. Thus, this metric is of critical importance for delay-critical applications that require tight monitoring of the human pose. Nonetheless, the FPS metric does not provide any information on the accuracy of the HPE estimation outcome.

In terms of CPU utilization, we can see that all methods have similar performances, ranging from 40% to even 100% at a given instance, with MoveNet exhibiting the highest CPU requirements on average (61%), followed by OpenPose (59.0%) and AlphaPose (54.7%). Note that AlphaPose attains a higher FPS as compared to OpenPose at a lower CPU utilization rate; however, AlphaPose also consumes GPU resources whereas OpenPose is CPU-native. MoveNet appears to be the most lightweight solution in terms of memory, using on the average about 2.9 GB of memory, lower even than the OpenVINO-based OpenPose (4.3 GB), which further uses the same backbone model. AlphaPose consumes 3.6 GB but, in combination with 30.7% GPU memory usage (out of the 16

GB available on the RTX A4000 GPU card), it reaches a total of 8.5 GB on the average. Measurements of the GPU usage are applicable only for the GPU-optimized AlphaPose, which on the average seems to consume about a third of the GPU potential at 37.5% and to require 100.1 Watts. The GPU consumption shown for Movenet and OpenPose (14.5 Watts), likely reflects the stand-by consumption of the GPU, highlighted also from the low standard deviation (std).

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE METRICS FOR HD AND VGA RANGE-OF-MOTION VIDEO

	Metric	Avg		Max		Min		Std	
		HD	VGA	HD	VGA	HD	VGA	HD	VGA
AlphaPose	RX (Mbps)	1.7	1.4	295.0	141.4	0.0	0.0	10.1	8.5
	TX (Mbps)	0.3	0.4	12.6	11.8	0.0	0.0	1.4	1.4
	CPU (%)	56.0	56.5	95.9	100.0	8.4	7.2	8.4	10.7
	RSS (GB)	3.6	4.1	3.7	4.5	2.6	3.0	0.1	0.2
	GPU (%)	36.7	44.3	72.0	63.0	0.0	0.0	7.6	10.7
	GPU Mem (%)	30.0	36.1	60.0	51.0	0.0	0.0	6.5	9.1
	GPU (Watts)	97.4	106.9	122.2	118.8	14.1	14.2	9.0	10.4
	OpenPose	RX (Mbps)	0.9	0.9	105.5	104.4	0.0	0.0	7.1
TX (Mbps)	0.1	0.1	5.5	5.2	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.5	
CPU (%)	58.6	60.0	92.8	97.1	4.4	7.2	8.6	7.4	
RSS (GB)	4.2	3.3	4.3	3.4	3.9	3.0	0.0	0.0	
GPU (%)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
GPU Mem (%)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
GPU (Watts)	14.5	14.4	15.8	15.7	14.0	13.9	0.3	0.4	
MoveNet	RX (Mbps)	3.3	3.3	238.0	247.2	0.0	0.0	15.5	17.3
	TX (Mbps)	0.7	0.9	12.8	6.5	0.0	0.0	2.0	2.3
	CPU (%)	58.6	62.0	100.0	86.5	4.5	17.2	12.6	7.1
	RSS (GB)	2.9	3.3	2.9	3.3	2.5	3.0	0.0	0.0
	GPU (%)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	GPU Mem (%)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	GPU (Watts)	14.5	14.4	15.6	15.5	14.1	13.9	0.3	0.4

Video FPS: AlphaPose (HD: 5.83, VGA: 7.12), OpenPose (HD: 3.01, VGA: 4.39), MoveNet (HD: 11.28, VGA: 16.40)

Table II provides performance values for the entire video duration in terms of mean, maximum, minimum and standard deviation values, assuming both the HD and VGA video resolutions. We note that in general, MoveNet attained the highest FPS. For the HD video in particular, we observe that AlphaPose and MoveNet exhibit high peak values in the required Rx throughput. Movenet is shown to deplete CPU usage but on the average it requires roughly the same CPU with the other models, as seen by the averages and the high standard deviation. Notably, all HPE models are shown to utilize roughly the same RSS memory, whereas the AlphaPose instance was the only one capable of utilizing GPU resources. Interestingly, we observe that the overall performance trend across the algorithms remains roughly the same even for the VGA video, including the Rx/Tx throughput requirements, provided that each algorithm consumes from the emulated IP camera video stream inputs in line with its capacity to process it by increasing its FPS performance, i.e., we do not observe a reduction in the Rx/Tx throughput requirements between the

HD and VGA video streams provided that the HPE service models tend to increase their FPS while utilizing roughly the same amount of resources, e.g., MoveNet increases its FPS from 5.83 to 16.50 FPS.

V. CONCLUSION

We have reviewed fundamental building blocks and backbone models for HPE service support in MEC-enabled networks and provided a thorough experimental study to assess the resource consumption of three state-of-the-art HPE models. We have highlighted key implementation issues and provided a fully automated natively containerized experimental setup capable to assess key performance metrics like Rx/Tx throughput, CPU and Memory RSS utilization as well as GPU utilization, memory usage and power consumption at the HPE Service host. Our results provide benchmark values for the deployment of MEC-enabled HPE services in proximity of mobile users while they also shed more light on achievable performance gains in communication overhead when HPE-based semantics-aware communications are deployed.

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